

From Vision to Implementation: Current Practices and Challenges of Software Management Plans in Research

Katarzyna Biernacka¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7294-4148>

¹ Technische Universität Berlin, <https://ror.org/03v4qjf40>

² ZB MED Information Centre for Life Sciences, <https://ror.org/0259fwx54>

³ Alfred-Wegener-Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, <https://ror.org/032e6b942>

⁴ Goethe University Frankfurt, <https://ror.org/04cvxb49>

⁵ Zuse Institute Berlin, <https://ror.org/02eva5865>

⁶ Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, <https://ror.org/01hcx6992>

⁷ Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Braunschweig, <https://ror.org/05r3f7h03>

⁸ Max Planck Digital Library, <https://ror.org/0061msm67>

⁹ Scientific Software Center, Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing, University of Heidelberg, <https://ror.org/04rcqnp59>

*Correspondence: Inga Ulusoy, inga.ulusoy@uni-heidelberg.de

Abstract

With the digitalisation of scientific practice and processes, including data-driven research and an increasing number of machine/deep learning models, the development of research software has become a fundamental component of scientific work. Proper management and documentation of the research software development process are thus essential for good scientific practice, reproducibility, and knowledge transfer. Similar to data management plans (DMPs), **software management plans** (SMPs) are an essential tool to document and organise research software development in all phases of its lifecycle: planning, design, coding, testing, sharing, and preserving [1-6]. While there are clear structural parallels between DMPs and SMPs, a key difference stands out: while DMPs have now established themselves as a kind of quasi-standard in many disciplines, SMPs have yet to achieve a comparable adoption.

One factor pushing the spread of DMPs was the obligation set by funding bodies. While topics that are addressed by SMPs are already touched upon in many funding applications, SMPs as a tool have not yet found broad adoption: they are currently a common **discussion topic in scientific councils** but are rarely implemented. Why this discrepancy?

To answer this question, we are taking a twofold approach. First, we are conducting **qualitative interviews** with decision-makers within funding organisations in Germany, the United Kingdom, and Australia. The focus lies on the current and future use of SMPs, as well as their

effectiveness for documentation, reporting, and communication. The results will be documented and made accessible as soon as possible.

In parallel, a second group is conducting a **quantitative survey** among scientists, infrastructure providers, and other potential user groups. The focus lies on usage practices, the acceptance, and the user-friendliness of SMPs. The anonymised results will be published as open research data.

Our conference contribution brings together the **findings** from both approaches, **involving different stakeholders in the current debate on the use of SMPs** in Germany and other countries. At the same time, it highlights current problems and key challenges reported by both funding organisations and the scientific community, while also offering recommendations for future solutions.

Keywords: Software Management Plans, Research Software, Research Funding Agencies

Resources

Elaborated survey results (in preparation, expected to be completed before August 2025)

Elaborated interviews results (in preparation, expected to be completed before August 2025)

Author contributions

KB: Conceptualization; Investigation; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

IU: Conceptualization; Investigation; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

YVG: Conceptualization; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

GL: Conceptualization; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

DW: Conceptualization; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

LJC: Conceptualization; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

AS: Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Visualization

MR: Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Visualization

BF: Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Visualization

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

LJC's work on Software Management Plans is part of the NFDI4DataScience project, funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) under the grant Nr. 460234259 (<https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/projekt/460234259>).

Acknowledgement

Parts of the authors belong to the DINI/nestor Workgroup Research Data (<https://dini.de/ag/dininestor-ag-forschungsdaten>).

KB gratefully acknowledges the support of the Cluster of Excellence UniSysCat (EXC 2008–390540038) funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) for enabling the contribution to this collaborative work (<https://www.unisyscat.de/>).

We gratefully acknowledge all interview and survey participants for their time, insights, and contributions to this project.

References

- [1] Y. V. Grossmann, G. Lanza, K. Biernacka, T. Hasler, K. Helbig, “Software Management Plans – Current Concepts, Tools, and Application”, *Data Science Journal*, vol. 23, no. 43, pp. 1–16, September 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-043>
- [2] Y. V. Grossmann, G. Lanza, K. Biernacka, T. Hasler, K. Helbig, “Bereitstellung von Software Management Plänen – Warum, wozu und wie funktioniert das?”. Presented at the 25. DINI-Jahrestagung, Potsdam, September 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13753493>
- [3] L. J. Castro, O. Giraldo, L. Geist, N. Quiñones, D. Solanki, D. Rebholz-Schuhmann, “Machine-actionable Software Management Plan Ontology (maSMP Ontology)” (2.1.0), 2024, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10582073>
- [4] L. J. Castro, L. Geist, E. Gonzalez, M. Gonzalez-Ocanto, Y. V. Grossmann, T. Pronk, D. Solanki, C. Utrilla Guerrero, D. Wallace, J. Windeck “Five Minutes to Write a Software Management Plan – A Machine-actionable Approach to Simplify the Creation of SMPs”, 2023, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10374839>
- [5] C. Martínez-Ortiz, P. Martínez Lavanchy, L. Sesink, B. G. Olivier, J. Meakin, M. de Jong, M. Cruz, “Practical guide to Software Management Plans” (1.1), 2023, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7589725>
- [6] R. Alves, D. Bampalikis, L. J. Castro, J. M. Fernández, J. Harrow, M. Kuzak, ... A. Via, “ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences”, 2021, BioHackrXiv, <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/k8znb>